

Serious Games for Food Waste Reduction: A Qualitative Review

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Abstract—Serious games provide interactive learning experiences that promote behavioral change in sustainability challenges, including food waste reduction. This study presents a qualitative review of nine serious games designed to influence food waste behaviors. Using the Playful Learning Framework, the review synthesizes research on game mechanics, educational approaches, and behavioral outcomes. Findings indicate that serious games improve food storage knowledge, enhance meal planning, and foster waste-conscious behaviors. However, gaps remain in long-term retention, community-driven engagement, and cross-platform effectiveness. Future research should explore multiplayer interaction, policy-driven applications, and longitudinal assessments to evaluate sustained behavioral change.

Index Terms—Serious Games, Food Waste, Behavioral Change, Educational Technology.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Household Food Waste and Its Challenges

Household food waste is a persistent issue with profound environmental, social, and economic consequences. It exacerbates climate change through methane emissions, contributes to biodiversity loss, and intensifies global food insecurity [1]–[4]. Food waste results from multiple factors, including consumer behavior, misinterpretation of food labels, storage practices, and meal planning habits [5]–[7]. Despite regulatory efforts and awareness campaigns, achieving long-term behavioral change remains challenging, requiring interactive and engaging interventions [8].

The European Union (EU) has established the Waste Framework Directive, which mandates monitoring and prevention measures for food waste reduction across the supply chain [9]. Consumer education is central to this framework, particularly regarding use-by and best-before date labeling, as misinterpretation leads to unnecessary disposal of food that is still safe for consumption [9].

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B. Serious Games as a Behavior Change Tool

Serious games have emerged as a promising method for engaging users in sustainability challenges, including food waste reduction [10]–[12]. For example, Menon et al. [13] developed a serious game to enhance user engagement in waste categorization. Unlike conventional education strategies, serious games immerse players in decision-making scenarios, reinforcing problem-solving skills and behavioral adaptation [14], [15]. Studies suggest that game-based interventions can enhance knowledge retention, strengthen motivation, and encourage sustainable habits [4], [16].

Recent research highlights the potential of mobile-based serious games in promoting sustainable food practices, particularly among children and households [17] [18].

C. Objectives

This review synthesizes findings on serious games designed to influence food waste behaviors. It evaluates game mechanics, educational strategies, and observed behavioral outcomes to identify critical gaps in research and practice. The study addresses the following research questions:

- RQ1: Who are the primary users targeted by serious games for food waste reduction?
- RQ2: What game elements and strategies are used to encourage sustainable behaviors?
- RQ3: What behavioral outcomes have been observed in players?

By examining the effectiveness of existing serious games, this review provides insights for designing future interventions that enhance engagement, scalability, and long-term impact on food waste reduction behaviors.

II. METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative narrative review to synthesize research on serious games for food waste reduction, focusing on game mechanics, learning strategies, and behavioral

outcomes [19]. The Playful Learning Framework [20] categorizes game mechanics into cognitive, motivational, affective, and sociocultural dimensions, structuring the evaluation of behavioral impact.

A structured search was conducted across ACM Digital Library, IEEE Xplore, Scopus, and Google Scholar using the query:

("serious games" OR "game-based learning") AND ("food waste") AND ("behavior change")

Inclusion criteria: Peer-reviewed studies (2018-2024) focusing on serious games addressing food waste, employing mixed-methods, experimental, or observational designs. Exclusion criteria: Gamification-only applications, non-interactive tools, and non-peer-reviewed studies.

The search retrieved 130 records, with 9 studies selected after AI-assisted screening via ASReview [19], ensuring a focused and rigorous selection of relevant literature.

III. RESULTS

A. Platforms, Target and Engagement

The effectiveness of serious games in food waste reduction depends on platform accessibility and user engagement. As shown in Table I, mobile platforms dominate (5/9 studies), providing accessibility for children and households. PC-based games (3/9) support cognitive learning, while VR (1/9) enhances emotional engagement.

TABLE I: Study Platforms, Design Focus, and Target Audience

Study	Platform	Design Focus	Audience/Target
Verloop 2018 [21]	PC	Cognitive	General public
Grüter 2021 [22]	PC	Sociocultural	General public
Sinclear 2021 [14]	PC	Affective	General public
Seiler 2022 [15]	VR	Affective	General users
Vasconcelos et al. 2023 [18]	Mobile	Cognitive/Motivational	Children and families
Jespersen 2023 [23]	Mobile	Cognitive	Households
Löchtefeld 2023 [24]	Mobile	Motivational	Households
Vasconcelos 2023 [25]	Mobile	Cognitive	Children
Olim et al. 2024 [17]	Mobile	Cognitive/Motivational	Children

B. Behavioral Outcomes

Serious games have demonstrated positive impacts on food waste reduction across multiple studies. As summarized in Table II. Interventions ranged from brief lessons to multi-week challenges [10], [21], [23].

TABLE II: Characteristics of Included Studies

Author	Research Design	Key Findings
Verloop 2018 [21]	Qualitative	Effective data collection on food waste behavior through serious game
Grüter 2021 [22]	Case Study	Increased intention to donate and share food
Sinclear 2021 [14]	Experimental	Emotional engagement drives awareness and behavior change
Seiler 2022 [15]	Experimental (VR)	Increased food waste awareness via immersive simulation
Vasconcelos et al. 2023 [18]	Mixed Methods	Family engagement in food waste reduction
Jespersen 2023 [23]	Longitudinal (Observational)	Improved long-term memory retention for sustainable behaviors
Löchtefeld 2023 [24]	Experimental	Fridge sorting game reduced food waste
Vasconcelos 2023 [25]	Mixed Methods	Positive cognitive and life skill development
Olim et al. 2024 [17]	Experimental	Increased children's knowledge of food storage and engagement

C. Game Mechanics and Learning Strategies

Serious games employ different mechanics to influence food waste behaviors. Table III summarizes these approaches: cognitive strategies (storage and planning tasks) [17], [18] enhance knowledge retention; motivational elements (goal-setting) [24] reinforce habits; affective techniques (VR, storytelling) [14], [15] strengthen emotional engagement; and sociocultural approaches (community-driven actions) [18], [22] promote shared responsibility.

TABLE III: Playful Learning Framework Synthesis

Perspective	Game Mechanics	Impact
Cognitive	Quizzes, planning tasks, storage mechanics	Enhanced food waste awareness and prevention
Motivational	Progress tracking, rewards	Increased engagement and behavior change
Affective	VR, emotional narratives	Stronger personal responsibility and empathy
Sociocultural	Multiplayer/social components	Increased communal waste reduction actions

D. Research Questions Answers

RQ1: Who are the primary users targeted by serious games for food waste reduction? Serious games targeted children (Vasconcelos et al. 2023 [18], Olim et al. 2024 [17]), households (Verloop 2018 [21], Jespersen 2023 [23]), and general users (Seiler 2022 [15], Grüter 2021 [22]). Table I summarizes these distributions.

RQ2: What behavioral outcomes have been observed in players? Studies report increased awareness, improved food management, and engagement through gamification (Table II). However, long-term effects remain underexplored.

RQ3: What game elements and strategies are used to encourage sustainable behaviors? Games applied cognitive (planning, storage tasks) [18], motivational (goal-setting) [24], affective (VR, storytelling) [15], and sociocultural (community-driven) [22] strategies. Table III categorizes these approaches.

IV. CONCLUSION

This review examined nine serious games designed to influence food waste reduction behaviors. The findings suggest that serious games can effectively enhance engagement, promote learning, and encourage sustainable food practices. However, most studies focused on short-term effects, with limited research on long-term behavioral change.

Also, reported outcomes rely on self-reported data, whose low validity may compromise intervention assessments [26].

Despite methodological limitations, serious games represent a valuable educational tool that can complement broader sustainability efforts. Future research should investigate long-term retention, the effectiveness of different game elements, and cross-platform comparisons to maximize impact. Collaborations between game developers, researchers, and policymakers could help design more scalable and evidence-based interventions for food waste reduction.

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